

A Photo Guide to Deep-Sea Fishes of Coral, Canyon, Seep and Soft Sediment Habitats along the Continental Slope (Texas to West Florida), Western Central Atlantic

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Background

Deep-sea fishes (>300 m) are abundant and diverse along the continental slope from Texas to West Florida, US in the Western Central Atlantic. However, few *in situ*, publicly available photos of fishes exist for confirmed identifications. Recent expeditions (NOAA Ship *Okeanos Explorer* EX1202L2, EX1711, EX1803) from 2012, 2017, 2018, (NOAA Ship *Nancy Foster* NF2206) from 2022, and (NOAA Ship *Pisces* PC23-02-L2) from 2023, provided high-resolution images of many fish species inhabiting cold-water coral habitats, submarine canyons, cold seeps and soft sediment at depths ranging from 304-2797 m. From these expeditions, we provide confirmed identifications of 116 adult fish species (and one juvenile on page 109), with several morphological characters to aid in identification (see Carpenter, 2002; McEachran and Fechhelm, 1998, 2005; Froese and Pauly, 2025). The majority (87%) of species in this guide are demersal. Although this only represents 8% of all fish species known in the Western Central Atlantic from Texas to West Florida (McEachran and Fechhelm 1998, 2005), this guide serves as a useful tool for identifying fishes in deep waters. All species names follow valid, accepted taxonomy based on Eschmeyer's *Catalog of Fishes* (Fricke et al., 2022).

The images in the guide are organized taxonomically (based on Fricke et al., 2022). Each photo is labeled with the dive number and depth of observation. A complete list of fish observations is provided in Table 1, including locality information and coordinates based on the starting latitude and longitude of each dive. The guide is designed to assist scientists in quickly identifying demersal fishes while at sea and complements a companion guide to deep-sea fishes along the US Atlantic margin (McIver and Quattrini, 2022). The guide is to be published on *Zenodo* to ensure it is open accessible, rapidly available, citable, and version-controlled for ongoing updates. Additional fish species will be added as new images are acquired.

Table 1. Location, depth of observation, known depth range, and date of fish species observed in ROV videos. Fishes are listed in order of photo guide. Latitude and longitude were taken from the start of dive location. Depth distribution range was included for each species, following Froese and Pauly (2025) and Robertson and Van Tassell (2023). N/A=data is not available from NOAA due to site is a shipwreck (Cultural Sites) or CTD not functioning. EX=Okeanos Explorer, NF=Nancy Foster; PC=Pisces.

Species	Dive	Date	Depth of observ. (m)	Depth range of species (m)	On Bottom Latitude (North)	On Bottom Longitude (West)
<i>Eptatretus minor</i>	EX1711-D03	12/2/17	742	300-400	25.6797	-84.6204
<i>Centroscyllium fabricii</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	601	180-2250	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Scyliorhinus retifer</i>	EX1202L2-D02	3/22/12	404	36-750	26.4413	-84.7514
<i>Galeus arae</i>	EX1803-D11	4/29/18	530	250-750	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Fenestraja cf. plutonia</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	531	290-750	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Dactylobatus clarkii</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	796	475-1000	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Rajella bathyphila</i>	EX1711-D10	12/12/17	1581	600-2300	27.0443	-91.1926
<i>Rajella purpuriventralis</i>	EX1803-D03	4/16/18	1515	922-1260	27.0108	-91.6739
<i>Harriotta raleighana</i>	EX1711-D10	12/12/17	620	200-3100	27.0443	-91.1926
<i>Hydrolagus mirabilis</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	803	450-1933	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Hydrolagus mirabilis</i>	EX1711-D17	12/20/17	1048	450-1933	28.9656	-88.1950
<i>Aldrovandia affinis</i>	EX1803-D13	4/30/18	2158	730-2560	24.9169	-84.4895
<i>Aldrovandia gracilis</i>	EX1803-D07	4/20/18	2164	460-2560	26.4707	-91.7281
<i>Aldrovandia oleosa</i>	EX1711-D10	12/12/17	1612	1200-1900	27.0443	-91.1926
<i>Aldrovandia phalacra</i>	EX1711-D02	12/1/17	2275	500-2300	24.6210	-84.1029
<i>Halosaurus guentheri</i>	EX1711-D17	12/20/17	1054	550-1600	28.9656	-88.1950
<i>Halosaurus ovenii</i>	EX1711-D17	12/20/17	1048	440-1700	28.9656	-88.1950
<i>Notacanthus bonaparte</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	796	487-2000	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Polyacanthonotus challengerii</i>	EX1711-D10	12/12/17	1605	777-4560	27.0443	-91.1926
<i>Polyacanthonotus merretti</i>	EX1803-D07	4/20/18	2220	598-2000	26.4707	-91.7281
<i>Polyacanthonotus rissoanus</i>	EX1711-D05	12/4/17	2118	500-2875	27.3538	-85.4366
<i>Atractodenchelys phrix</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	761	385-425	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Dysommia rugosa</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	562	260-775	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Ilyophis blachei</i>	EX1803-D07	4/20/18	2182	580-2023	26.4707	-91.7281
<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	EX1711-D09	12/11/17	1179	450-3120	27.5255	-89.6997
<i>Synaphobranchus brevidorsalis</i>	EX1803-D02	4/13/18	N/A	230-3000	N/A	N/A
<i>Synaphobranchus kaupii</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	896	120-4800	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Pseudophichthys splendens</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	805	37-1647	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Conger cf. oceanicus</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	1-477	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Nettastoma melanura</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	762	0-1647	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Venefica procera</i>	EX1803-D07	4/20/18	2209	326-2304	26.4707	-91.7281
<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	EX1711-D10	12/12/17	1606	900-3500	27.0443	-91.1926
<i>Manducus maderensis</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	576	0-850	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Argentina striata</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	95-500	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Alepocephalus agassizii</i>	EX1803-D06	4/19/18	1059	600-2500	27.0961	-92.8207
<i>Conocara macropteron</i>	EX1202L2-D14	4/3/12	1443	800-2200	28.7342	-88.2435
<i>Chlorophthalmus agassizi</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	400	50-1000	27.7035	-92.2204

<i>Parasudis truculenta</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	405	133-1170	27.7035	-92.2204
<i>Bathypterois bigelowi</i>	EX1711-D01	11/30/17	728	377-986	24.6516	-83.9103
<i>Bathypterois grallator</i>	EX1711-D02	12/1/17	2274	878-4720	24.6210	-84.1029
<i>Bathypterois grallator</i>	EX1803-D05	4/18/18	2779	878-4720	26.1447	-94.8667
<i>Bathypterois phenax</i>	EX1711-D02	12/1/17	2303	800-2657	24.6210	-84.1029
<i>Bathypterois quadrifilis</i>	EX1202L2-D14	4/3/12	1368	402-1408	28.7342	-88.2435
<i>Bathypterois viridensis</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	808	476-1477	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Bathytrophops marionae</i>	EX1803-D10	4/27/18	2578	692-1920	27.7054	-85.7483
<i>Ipnotis murrayi</i>	EX1803-D09	4/26/18	2132	1789-3477	28.1233	-86.6588
<i>Bathysaurus mollis</i>	EX1803-D13	4/30/18	2215	1550-4903	24.9169	-84.4895
<i>Lampanyctus</i> sp.	EX1711-D09	12/11/17	1127	N/A	27.5255	-89.6997
<i>Lobianchia gemellarii</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	398	25-800	27.7035	-92.2204
<i>Acanthonus armatus</i>	EX1711-D02	12/1/17	2309	1171-4415	24.6210	-84.1029
<i>Acanthonus armatus</i>	EX1711-D05	12/4/17	2109	1171-4415	27.3538	-85.4366
<i>Acanthonus armatus</i>	EX1803-D09	4/26/18	2226	1171-4415	28.1233	-86.6588
<i>Barathrodemus manatinus</i>	EX1711-D11	12/13/17	2037	1060-1318	26.4225	-92.3508
<i>Bassozetus normalis</i>	EX1803-D08	4/25/18	2460	1760-5062	28.2837	-87.2230
<i>Bassozetus taenia</i>	EX1711-D05	12/4/17	1869	1783-5605	27.3538	-85.4366
<i>Bassozetus taenia</i>	EX1711-D06	12/5/17	2070	1783-5605	28.0037	-86.4399
<i>Benthocometes robustus</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	527	500-1000	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Dicrolene introniger</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	805	700-1785	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Lucibrotula corethromycter</i>	EX1803-D14	5/1/18	2283	220-1830	24.5744	-84.2736
<i>Mastigopterus imperator</i>	EX1803-D05	4/18/18	2788	394-2365	26.1447	-94.8667
<i>Monomitopus</i> sp.	EX1803-D06	4/19/18	1081	N/A	27.0961	-92.8207
<i>Penopus microphthalmus</i>	EX1803-D10	4/27/18	2990	960-3535	27.7054	-85.7483
<i>Porogadus miles</i>	EX1711-D08	12/10/17	2151	1000-5055	27.7146	-88.4445
<i>Spectrunculus grandis</i>	EX1711-D10	12/12/17	1583	800-4300	27.0443	-91.1926
<i>Bythites gerdae</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	866	86-832	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Cataetyx laticeps</i>	EX1803-D03	4/16/18	1520	500-2400	27.0108	-91.6739
<i>Cataetyx laticeps</i>	EX1803-D07	4/20/18	2183	500-2400	26.4707	-91.7281
<i>Diplacanthopoma</i> cf. <i>brachysoma</i>	EX1711-D01	11/30/17	786	460-1670	24.6516	-83.9103
<i>Gadomus arcuatus</i>	EX1711-D17	12/20/17	1050	610-1370	28.9656	-88.1950
<i>Gadomus longifilis</i>	EX1803-D06	4/19/18	1054	630-2165	27.0961	-92.8207
<i>Coelorinchus caelorhincus</i>	EX1711-D03	12/2/17	742	90-1485	25.6797	-84.6204
<i>Coryphaenoides mediterraneus</i>	EX1711-D08	12/10/17	2161	1000-4262	27.7146	-88.4445
<i>Coryphaenoides mexicanus</i>	EX1711-D09	12/11/17	1135	110-1600	27.5255	-89.6997
<i>Coryphaenoides rudis</i>	EX1711-D08	12/10/17	2151	600-2380	27.7146	-88.4445
<i>Coryphaenoides zaniophorus</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	804	400-2375	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Kumba</i> sp.	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	733	N/A	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Kumba</i> sp.	EX1803-D06	4/19/18	1061	N/A	27.0961	-92.8207
<i>Nezumia aequalis</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	576	200-2320	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Nezumia cyrano</i>	NF2206-D01	8/20/22	1566	860-915	28.6805	-88.3421
<i>Nezumia suilla</i>	EX1711-D09	12/11/17	1142	860-915	27.5255	-89.6997
<i>Ventrifossa</i> sp.	EX1803-D15	5/2/18	446	N/A	24.2802	-82.2576
<i>Laemonema barbatulum</i>	EX1803-D15	5/2/18	487	50-1620	24.2802	-82.2576
<i>Laemonema goodebeanorum</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	535	180-792	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Laemonema goodebeanorum</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	515	180-792	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Urophycis cirrata</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	533	27-684	28.1506	-89.7614

<i>Merluccius albidus</i>	EX1711-D01	11/30/17	720	80-1170	24.6516	-83.9103
<i>Lophiodes beroe</i>	EX1711-D03	12/2/17	709	347-860	25.6797	-84.6204
<i>Lophiodes beroe</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	639	347-860	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Lophiodes reticulatus</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	64-820	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Sladenia shaefersi</i>	EX1803-D06	4/19/18	1057	900-1200	27.0961	-92.8207
<i>Chaunax pictus</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	454	200-1000	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Chaunax suttkusi</i>	EX1711-D03	12/2/17	741	220-1362	25.6797	-84.6204
<i>Chaunax suttkusi</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	618	220-1362	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Dibranchius atlanticus</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	398	45-1300	27.7035	-92.2204
<i>Stephanoberyx monae</i>	EX1711-D17	12/20/17	1054	945-4777	28.9656	-88.1950
<i>Gephyroberyx darwinii</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	9-1210	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Hoplostethus occidentalis</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	524	485-550	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Beryx decadactylus</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	505	110-1300	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Zenion hololepis</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	180-700	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Cyttopsis rosea</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	411	150-730	27.7035	-92.2204
<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	50-1100	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	EX1803-D15	5/2/18	458	50-1100	24.2802	-82.2576
<i>Idiastion kyphos</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	435	439-622	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Idiastion kyphos</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	434	439-622	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Phenacoscopus nebris</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	531	350-480	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Setarches guentheri</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	509	150-840	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Trachyscorpia cristulata</i>	EX1803-D12	4/29/18	434	130-1389	25.6046	-84.5507
<i>Peristedion greyae</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	180-1071	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Peristedion truncatum</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	518	155-910	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Synagrops bellus</i>	EX1711-D03	12/2/17	695	60-910	25.6797	-84.6204
<i>Hyporthodus niveatus</i>	PC2302L2-D14	7/9/23	323	30-525	N/A	N/A
<i>Anthias woodsi</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	90-475	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Epigonus denticulatus</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	535	130-830	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	795	550-1300	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Epigonus occidentalis</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	734	144-735	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Epigonus occidentalis</i>	EX1803-D04	4/17/18	761	144-735	27.0117	-93.9111
<i>Epigonus oligolepis</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	500	380-660	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Epigonus sp.</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	N/A	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Lycenchelys bullisi</i>	EX1711-D14	12/17/17	793	732-750	27.6650	-91.3437
<i>Lycenchelys bullisi</i>	EX1711-D17	12/20/17	1053	732-750	28.9656	-88.1950
Chiasmodontidae	EX1711-D09	12/11/17	1133	N/A	27.5255	-89.6997
<i>Bembrops gobioides</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	514	100-825	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Centrodraco acanthopoma</i>	EX1803-D11	4/28/18	521	170-594	26.3762	-84.7592
<i>Centrodraco acanthopoma</i>	EX1803-D15	5/2/18	311	170-594	24.2802	-82.2576
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	EX1711-D03	12/2/17	698	200-850	25.6797	-84.6204
<i>Ariomma bondi</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	616	25-640	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Hyperoglyphe perciformis</i>	EX1711-D04	12/3/17	386	0-1066	26.4448	-84.7608
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	EX1711-D15	12/18/17	533	0-2878	28.1506	-89.7614
<i>Monolene sessilicauda</i>	EX1803-D15	5/2/18	364	150-550	24.2802	-82.2576
<i>Poecilopsetta beanii</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	408	155-1636	27.7035	-92.2204
<i>Symphurus marginatus</i>	EX1711-D13	12/16/17	408	37-750	27.7035	-92.2204

Myxinidae (Hagfishes)

Eyes reduced; no paired fins; eel-shaped body

***Eptatretus minor* (Gulf Hagfish)**

Body light brown; dorsal midline whitish; single, large median nostril

Etmopteridae (Lantern Sharks)

Small sharks; spiracles present, large and just behind eyes; 2 dorsal fins with a grooved spine; 1st dorsal usually smaller than 2nd dorsal; no anal fin; body and fins greyish to blackish brown

***Centroscyllium fabricii* (Black Dogfish)**

1st dorsal fin low; 1st dorsal fin spine short; 2nd dorsal fin considerably larger than 1st; 2nd dorsal fin spine elongated; color is blackish brown above and below

Scyliorhinidae (Cat Sharks)

Small sharks; 1st dorsal originates over pelvic fin; no dorsal fin spines; usually with dark spots, blotches, bars or saddles

Scyliorhinus retifer (Chain Catshark)

Color pattern of dark lines in reticular pattern

Pentanchidae (Deepwater Catsharks)

Small sharks; 2 small dorsal fins; anal fin present; no internal crest over the orbits of the eyes

EX1803-D11
530 m

EX1803-D11
530 m

***Galeus arae* (Roughtail Catshark)**

2nd dorsal fin smaller than 1st; pectoral fins large; marbled pattern of spots and saddles

Gurgesiellidae (Pygmy Skates)

Very small to small rays; rhombic to heart-shaped disc; pelvic fins deeply notched; tail has 2 small dorsal fins; skin on dorsal surface variably covered with small denticles

***Fenestraja cf. plutonia* (Pluto Skate)**

Dorsal surface pale brown to purplish brown with irregular dark blotches over disc and cross-bands on tail; often sits with tail held very straight

Rajidae (Skates)

Rhombic or heart-shaped disc; tail slender; pelvic fins bilobed; 2 small dorsal fins

Dactylobatus clarkii (Clark's Finger Skate)

Disc round; dorsal surface of disc grey-brown with pairs of dark-ringed white spots; dorsal surface with sparse denticles; 3 rows of thorns along tail

Rajidae (Skates)

Head, body and pectorals form flattened rhomboidal disc; 2 small dorsal fins near rear of tail; top of disc usually with thorns at eyes, nape; 2nd dorsal fin smaller than 1st; marbled pattern of spots and saddles

Rajella bathyphila (Deepwater Ray)

Disc heart shaped, without definite markings; outer edges of pectoral and pelvic fins shading to darker; big thorns on the midline behind the eyes to the pelvic fins; underside with large white areas and blotches

Rajidae (Skates)

Head, body and pectorals form flattened rhomboidal disc; 2 small dorsal fins near rear of tail; top of disc usually with thorns at eyes, nape; 2nd dorsal fin smaller than 1st; marbled pattern of spots and saddles

Rajella purpuriventralis (Purplebelly Skate)

Disc heart shaped; snout relatively long, pointed and stiff; upper surface uniformly covered with small denticles; color is purplish-black

Rhinochimaeridae (Longnose Chimaeras)

Body compressed, elongate, tapering to a filamentous tail; head very large; snout very long, elongate, spear-like; eyes large; nostrils large

Harriotta raleighana (Narrownose Chimaera)

Snout very long, spear-like, wide at base, tapering to a fine point, tip curved up; anal fin absent; caudal fin elongate, lower lobe larger than upper

Chimaeridae (Shortnose Chimaeras)

Large head; blunt snout; tail tapering to filament; large eyes; large pectoral fins

Hydrolagus mirabilis (Large-eyed Rabbit Fish)

Dark brown in color; 1st dorsal fin short-based with strong spine; 2nd dorsal low, long based and concave in middle; anal fin absent; extremely long caudal filament

Halosauridae (Halosaurs)

Mouth inferior; single, short-based dorsal fin; long, tapering tail; no caudal fin

Aldrovandia affinis (Gilbert's Halosaurid Fish)

Body dirty white to grey-brown in color; insertion of the pelvic fin only slightly anterior to the origin of the dorsal fin; no scales on top of head or opercle

Halosauridae (Halosaurs)

Mouth inferior; single, short-based dorsal fin; long, tapering tail; no caudal fin

Aldrovandia gracilis

Body white to silvery white in color; cheeks bluish in color; no scales on top of head or opercle

Halosauridae (Halosaurs)

Mouth inferior; single, short-based dorsal fin; long, tapering tail; no caudal fin

Aldrovandia oleosa

Scales absent on top of head and opercle; pre-oral length is very short; 1st dorsal ray very short; body dark brown, head black

Halosauridae (Halosaurs)

Mouth inferior; single, short-based dorsal fin; long, tapering tail; no caudal fin

***Aldrovandia phalacra* (Hawaiian Halosaurid Fish)**

Body grey in color; head silvery blue on top and sides, darker below; snout, head and opercle scaleless

Halosauridae (Halosaurs)

Mouth inferior; single, short-based dorsal fin; long, tapering tail; no caudal fin

Halosaurus guentheri

Scales on top of head and opercle; color is tan dorsally and ventrally

Halosauridae (Halosaurs)

Mouth inferior; single, short-based dorsal fin; long, tapering tail; no caudal fin

EX1711-D17
1048 m

Halosaurus ovenii

Scales on top of head and opercle; irregular two-tone color pattern, pale tan dorsally, light ventrally

Notacanthidae (Deep Sea Spiny Eels)

Mouth small, inferior; dorsal fin a series of isolated spinous rays; long, tapering tail, no caudal fin

***Notacanthus bonaparte* (Shortfin Spiny Eel)**

Grey or pink in color; short snout, long head, mouth on the underside; males are smaller and have enlarged nasal rosettes

Notacanthidae (Deep Sea Spiny Eels)

Mouth small, inferior; dorsal fin a series of isolated spinous rays; long, tapering tail, no caudal fin

EX1711-D10
1605 m

***Polyacanthonotus challengerii* (Longnose Tapirfish)**

Anterior and posterior nostrils set far apart; mouth extends back to the anterior edge of the orbit; reaches half a meter total length

Notacanthidae (Deep Sea Spiny Eels)

Mouth small, inferior; dorsal fin a series of isolated spinous rays; long, tapering tail, no caudal fin

EX1803-D07
2220 m

EX1803-D07
2220 m

Polyacanthonotus merretti

Anterior and posterior nostrils set far apart; mouth extends back to the orbit; edge of gill cover black; inside of mouth black; small species, reaches a third of a meter total length

Notacanthidae (Deep Sea Spiny Eels)

Mouth small, inferior; dorsal fin a series of isolated spinous rays; long, tapering tail, no caudal fin

***Polyacanthonotus rissoanus* (Smallmouth Spiny Eel)**

Mouth small, falling far short of anterior edge of orbit; dorsal fin origin anterior to pectorals; color is off-white to tan to light grey; anal fin dark brown; margin of opercular flap black; reaches half a meter total length

Synphobranchidae (Cutthroat Eels)

Small to medium size; mouth extends beyond eyes; dorsal, anal fins well developed; eyes well developed; gill openings very close or conjoined

***Atractodenchelys phrix* (Arrowtooth Eel)**

Pectoral fins present; dorsal fin origin far forward; anus far forward; lower jaw distinctly shorter than upper; body distinctly bicolored for most of its length, dark above and pale below

Synaphobranchidae (Cutthroat Eels)

Small to medium size; mouth extends beyond eyes; dorsal, anal fins well developed; eyes well developed; gill openings very close or conjoined

Dysommima rugosa

Body light brownish in color, paler ventrally; dorsal, anal and caudal fins white in color

Synphobranchidae (Cutthroat Eels)

Small to medium size; mouth extends beyond eyes; dorsal, anal fins well developed; eyes well developed; gill openings very close or conjoined

***Ilyophis blachei* (Blache's Ooze Eel)**

Body whitish is color; robust body with high median fins; long lateral line; corner of jaw gape extends back only to rear margin of orbit

Synphobranchidae (Cutthroat Eels)

Small to medium size; mouth extends beyond eyes; dorsal, anal fins well developed; eyes well developed; gill openings very close or conjoined

***Ilyophis brunneus* (Muddy Arrowtooth Eel)**

Dark brown tinged with violet on snout; pores in lateral line very white; dorsal fin origin above tip of small pectoral fins; slender, tubular body

Synaphobranchidae (Cutthroat Eels)

Small to medium size; mouth extends beyond eyes; dorsal, anal fins well developed; eyes well developed; gill openings very close or conjoined

***Synaphobranchus brevidorsalis* (Shortdorsal Cutthroat Eel)**

Body robust; pectoral fins well developed and long; dorsal fin origin far behind anus; eyes large; color is medium to dark brown

Synphobranchidae (Cutthroat Eels)

Small to medium size; mouth extends beyond eyes; dorsal, anal fins well developed; eyes well developed; gill openings very close or conjoined

***Synphobranchus kaupii* (Kaup's Arrowtooth Eel)**

Head elongate; dorsal-fin origin well behind level of anus; dark purplish-grey in color

Congridae (Conger Eels)

Medium to large size; round in cross-section; eyes well developed; dorsal, anal and caudal fins present

Pseudophichthys splendens (Purplemouthed Conger)

Snout swollen, projecting; dorsal fin origin behind pectorals; pectoral fins small; tail tip soft and flexible

Congridae (Conger eels)

Medium to large size; round in cross-section; eyes well developed; dorsal, anal and caudal fins present

EX1711-D04
386 m

***Conger cf. oceanicus* (Conger Eel)**

Eyes large; pectoral fins present; dorsal fin begins behind base of pectoral; vertical fins with black edges

Nettastomatidae (Duckbill Eels)

Small to medium size; head slender; snout elongate; eyes well developed; tail slender, attenuate; dorsal and anal fins edged in black, especially posteriorly

***Nettastoma melanura* (Blackfin Sorcerer)**

Body very elongate; head and jaws elongate; posterior part of dorsal and anal fins with black margin

Nettastomatidae (Duckbill Eels)

Small to medium size; head slender; snout elongate; eyes well developed; tail slender, attenuate; dorsal and anal fins edged in black, especially posteriorly

Venefica procera (Short-snout Sorcerer)

Eyes small; snout very long; tip of snout with a fleshy pointed proboscis; top jaw overhanging

Gonostomatidae (Bristlemouths)

Body moderately elongate; head and body compressed; chin barbel absent; dorsal fin at or posterior to middle of body; 1 or more rows of discrete photophores on body

***Cyclothone obscura* (Hidden Bristlemouth)**

Photophores absent; dorsal adipose fin absent; anterior rays of dorsal and anal fins elongate; color is dark brown

Gonostomatidae (Bristlemouths)

Body moderately elongate; head and body compressed; chin barbel absent; dorsal fin at or posterior to middle of body; 1 or more rows of discrete photophores on body

Manducus maderensis

2 rows of ventral photophores; dorsum black-brown in color, sides silver

Argentinidae (Argentines)

Small fishes with elongate, compressed, silvery bodies; large eyes; small mouth; small adipose fin present; strongly forked tail

***Argentina striata* (Striated Argentine)**

Small fish with body elongate and translucent, head silver; small terminal mouth; adipose fin present

Alepocephalidae (Slickheads)

Slender bodies; soft watery flesh; dorsal and anal fins opposite and far back on the body; either naked skin or large cycloid scales

***Alepocephalus agassizii* (Agassiz's Slickhead)**

Body elongate with very large head and eyes; dorsal fin origin even with anal fin origin; scales present; uniformly black

Alepocephalidae (Slickheads)

Slender bodies; soft watery flesh; dorsal and anal fins opposite and far back on the body; either naked skin or large cycloid scales

Conocara macropteryum (Longfin Smooth-head)

Brown to black in color; anal fin is long based; dorsal fin much shorter than anal fin; no scales

Chlorophthalmidae (Greeneyes)

Eyes green with teardrop-shaped pupil; dorsal fin large; lower jaw terminal with bony tip

***Chlorophthalmus agassizi* (Shortnose Greeneye)**

Eyes large; head small; color is yellow-fawn with irregular oblique brown blotches on sides

Chlorophthalmidae (Greeneyes)

Eyes green with teardrop-shaped pupil; dorsal fin large; lower jaw terminal with bony tip

Parasudis truculenta (Longnose Greeneye)

Adipose fin present; snout depressed like a spatula; lower jaw protruding; eye large; color is pale grey with 4 dark saddles

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

***Bathypterois bigelowi* (Bigelow's Tripodfish)**

Body white, with irregular bands of reddish-purple, yellowish, or dark blue; 2 dark spots on caudal fin base

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

***Bathypterois grillator* (Tripodfish)**

Extremely long caudal and pelvic-fin rays; no adipose fin; color uniform black

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

***Bathypterois phenax* (Abyssal Tripodfish)**

Presence of subcaudal notch; adipose fin present; head and body black; fins black

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

***Bathypterois quadrifilis* (Fourfinger Tripodfish)**

Outer 2 pelvic rays prolonged to reach anal fin; subcaudal notch present; adipose fin present; body black with paler scale pocket margins

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

***Bathypterois viridensis* (Darkheaded Tripodfish)**

Body white with three dark bands; pelvic and lower caudal rays prolonged; subcaudal notch absent

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

EX1803-D10
2578 m

EX1803-D10
2578 m

***Bathytyphlops marionae* (Marion's Spiderfish)**

Body grey to brown in color; head dark; no eyes; adipose fin absent

Ipnopidae (Tripod Fishes)

Eyes very small; caudal fin forked with lower lobe longer than upper; pectoral fin modified often with elongate rays; pelvic fin may possess elongate rays anteriorly

***Ipnopops murrayi* (Murray's Grideye Fish)**

Eye is flat, plate-like grid of light sensitive tissue on top of head; head and body black, eye patch pale; no adipose fin

Bathysauridae (Deepsea Lizardfishes)

Head very depressed; eyes small; upper jaw extending far beyond eye; whitish, grey or brown in color

***Bathysaurus mollis* (Highfin Lizardfish)**

Head depressed and bony; mouth large; color generally white, with peritoneum, branchial and buccal regions dark

Myctophidae (Lanternfishes)

Small fishes; head and eyes large; dorsal fin base at midbody; dorsal adipose fin present; photophores present; brown to black in color

***Lampanyctus* sp.**

Luminous gland is embedded in caudal peduncle; large eyes; dorsal fin origin posterior to pelvic fin; lateral photophores minute or absent

Myctophidae (Lanternfishes)

Small fishes; head and eyes large; dorsal fin base at midbody; dorsal adipose fin present; photophores present; brown to black in color

***Lobianchia gemellarii* (Cocco's Lantern Fish)**

2 sets of orbital photophores on head; deep forehead; low count of serial photophores

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Acanthonus armatus (Bony-eared Assfish)

Head large, body tapering, eye small; snout with prominent, bifid spine; opercular spine long, slender, extending well beyond rear margin of head; well developed spines at lower angle of preopercle

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Barathrodemus manatinus (Bighead Cusk Eel)

Head relatively large, inflated; pectoral fin reaches to anus or beyond

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Bassozetus normalis

Evenly rounded head, not depressed; large, prominent anterior nostrils; lateral line less noticeable and runs mid-laterally

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Bassozetus taenia

Snout inflated; eyes much smaller than snout; opercular spine weak or absent; preopercle without spines; 2 pseudobranchial filaments

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Benthocometes robustus (Robust Cusk Eel)

Head short and stubby; eyes equal to or greater than length of snout; opercle with 2 posteriorly directed spines

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Dicrolene introniger (Digitate Cusk Eel)

Snout blunt; eye large; lower 5-11 pectoral fin rays free and longer than upper ones; opercular spine strong and straight

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Luciobrotula corethromycter

Lateral line incomplete; snout is depressed with fleshy flaps; head and body brown, with fins dark brown; pectoral fins short and broad

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Mastigopterus imperator

Long, pectoral fin with many rays extending back freely like fingers; 3 incomplete lateral lines as a series of prominent white pores, 1 along the dorsal fin base; distinctly separate terminal flap-like caudal fin; opercular spine is flattened

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

EX1803-D06
1081 m

Monomitopus sp.

Opercle with 1 straight, rounded, strong spine with a single point; pelvic fins with 1 ray; head covered with scales; body color pale

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Penopus microphthalmus

Eye diameter (1.1-1.6% SL); almost fully scaled head; 4-7 preopercular spines

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

Porogadus miles (Slender Cuskeel)

All head spines are strong; opercular spine is sharp, strong; 3 lateral lines; color is charcoal gray to black

Ophidiidae (Cusk Eels)

Spine on opercle; scales present; dorsal-fin rays equal to or longer than anal-fin rays

EX1711-D10
1583 m

EX1711-D10
1583 m

Spectrunculus grandis (Pudgy Cuskeel)

Large, robust bodied fish; small scales uniformly over head and body; strong opercular spine; head bluntly rounded off; prominent raised rim around each forward placed anterior nostril; pelvic fins are two thin rays

Bythitidae (Viviparous Brotulas)

Spine on opercle; scales usually present; anterior nostril immediately above upper lip

EX1803-D04
866 m

***Bythites gerdae* (Deep Reef Brotula)**

Body short and robust; head very large, without scales; upper jaws end well behind eye; opercular spine strong, covered with skin; head and body color dark brown to blackish

Bythitidae (Viviparous Brotulas)

Spine on opercle; scales usually present; anterior nostril immediately above upper lip

Cataetyx laticeps

Body slender with dorsal and anal fins joined to the caudal fin; scales present on head and body; snout strongly depressed, projects beyond lower jaw; strong opercular spine; eyes with white rim; body color brown

Bythitidae (Viviparous Brotulas)

Spine on opercle; scales usually present; anterior nostril immediately above upper lip

***Diplacanthopoma cf. brachysoma* (Twospine Brotula)**

Lateral line dips suddenly midbody; opercular spine strong; scales present on body; body tapers to slender tail

Bathygadidae (Bathygadids)

Large terminal mouth; long tapering tail; no caudal fin; 2nd dorsal fin beginning immediately behind 1st

EX1711-D17
1050 m

Gadomus arcuatus (Doublethread Grenadier)

Chin barbels long and prominent; 1st fin rays of dorsal, pectoral and pelvic fins very elongated; color is brownish; fin membranes blackish

Bathygadidae (Bathygadids)

Large terminal mouth; long tapering tail; no caudal fin; 2nd dorsal fin beginning immediately behind 1st

Gadomus longifilis (Threadfin Grenadier)

Brownish in color; chin barbel longer than eye diameter; 1st fin ray of pectoral and pelvic fins elongated; 2nd fin ray of 1st dorsal fin elongated

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

***Coelorinchus caelorhincus* (Hollowsnout Grenadier)**

Snout short, head ridges strong; snout bears terminal scute that is wider than long; color is pale greyish brown with a series of broad saddle marks

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

Coryphaenoides mediterraneus (Mediterranean Grenadier)

Head scaled; blunt snout; 1st pelvic ray elongated; brown to dark brown in color

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

***Coryphaenoides mexicanus* (Mexican Grenadier)**

Acute snout; 1st pelvic ray elongated; brown in color with darker brown around nostrils and orbits

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

***Coryphaenoides rudis* (Bighead Grenadier)**

Blunt snout; 1st pelvic ray elongated; orbits are 16-26% TL; brown to light brown in color, tips of fins dark brown to black

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

Coryphaenoides zaniophorus (Thickbeard Grenadier)

Head large, completely scaled; orbits are ~30% TL; color is medium to dark brown; fins generally blackish

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

Kumba sp.

Color is dark; 2nd dorsal fin is distinctly separated from 1st and has shorter rays than anal fin

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

***Nezumia aequalis* (Common Atlantic Grenadier)**

Color is bluish to violet with distal part of 1st dorsal fin black; inner part of pelvic fin black; pectoral and anal fins dusky

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

***Nezumia cyrano* (Bluntnose Grenadier)**

2 large scutes present at snout tip; suborbital ridge developed; head fully scaled; brownish violet with brownish color predominantly on tail and back; snout and tips distinctly paler

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

Nezumia suilla

Terminal snout scutes small; suborbital ridge developed; head fully scaled; 1st dorsal fin tipped in black, the remainder clear; pelvic fins tipped with black

Macrouridae (Grenadiers)

Tail tapers to slender point; eyes large; 1st dorsal high, 2nd dorsal long-based; silvery along sides of head and body

Ventrifossa sp.

Shiny silver color; prominent black tip of 1st dorsal and black margins in the anal fin; extremely elongated and evenly tapered straight body and tail

Moridae (Codlings)

Large eyes; 1st dorsal triangular, 2nd dorsal long-based; anal fin long-based; pelvic fins thoracic; narrow caudal peduncle; small caudal fin

Laemonema barbatulum (Shortbeard Codling)

Distal end of caudal fin black; prolonged black spine on 1st dorsal fin

Moridae (Codlings)

Large eyes; 1st dorsal triangular, 2nd dorsal long-based; anal fin long-based; pelvic fins thoracic; narrow caudal peduncle; small caudal fin

EX1803-D11
535 m

EX1803-D12
515 m

Laemonema goodebeanorum

Distal $\frac{2}{3}$ of 1st dorsal fin and posterior edge of 2nd dorsal fin black

Phycidae (Phycid Hakes)

Short chin barbel; 2 dorsal fins; caudal fin rounded, well developed; pelvic fin has 2 long, slender rays

EX1711-D15
533 m

***Urophycis cirrata* (Gulf Hake)**

Chin barbel short; 'long dark mustache' along the upper jaw; very elongate pelvic rays, reaching past anus; body color is brownish

Merlucciidae (Merlucciid Hakes)

Mouth large; 1st dorsal short, triangular; 2nd dorsal and anal fin long-based and notched near midlength; caudal fin well developed, weakly forked; silver in color with dark blotches

***Merluccius albidus* (Offshore Silver Hake)**

Head long (27-32% of SL); color grey-brown above, remainder silvery white

Lophiidae (Goosefishes)

Mouth very large and wide; lower jaw projecting, numerous sharp teeth; head and anterior part of body depressed and very broad; skin often with fleshy flaps on head and/or body; pelvic fins on ventral surface of head anterior to pectoral fins; 1st cephalic spine modified into angling apparatus with esca

Lophiodes beroe (White Anglerfish)

Reddish to reddish brown background pigmentation with pale or white blotches; black illicium with pale esca

Lophiidae (Goosefishes)

Mouth very large and wide; lower jaw projecting, numerous sharp teeth; head and anterior part of body depressed and very broad; skin often with fleshy flaps on head and/or body; pelvic fins on ventral surface of head anterior to pectoral fins; 1st cephalic spine modified into angling apparatus with esca

***Lophiodes reticulatus* (Reticulated Goosefish)**

Top of head and body covered with a fine mesh or chain pattern

Lophiidae (Goosefishes)

Mouth very large and wide; lower jaw projecting, numerous sharp teeth; head and anterior part of body depressed and very broad; skin often with fleshy flaps on head and/or body; pelvic fins on ventral surface of head anterior to pectoral fins; 1st cephalic spine modified into angling apparatus with esca

Sladenia shaeferi (Shaefer's Anglerfish)

Head, body and fins mid-grey; head and body with numerous pale irregular rosettes and small patches of reticulating pale lines

Chaunacidae (Gapers)

Body rounded with very loose, flaccid skin; head very large & bearing open lateral-line canals; single short spine modified as angling apparatus located just behind snout; mouth large; generally pink, reddish, orange or rose-colored

***Chaunax pictus* (Pink Gaper)**

Rose or reddish-orange pigment; back with yellow spots; thread cluster blue-black at front

Chaunacidae (Gapers)

Body rounded with very loose, flaccid skin; head very large & bearing open lateral-line canals; single short spine modified as angling apparatus located just behind snout; mouth large; generally pink, reddish, orange or rose-colored

Chaunax suttkusi (Spotted Gaper)

Head and body pale to rosy pink; fins red; upper body with yellow spots; lure uniformly pale with dark threads

Ogcocephalidae (Batfishes)

Head strongly depressed into a circular or triangular disk; pectoral fins behind disc, elongate and leg-like; lure very short

Dibranchus atlanticus (Atlantic Batfish)

Tail long; spine at corner of operculum large; body and tail pale yellowish brown, spines paler; dorsal, tail and pectoral fins reddish

Stephanoberycidae (Pricklefishes)

Body and head subcylindrical; single dorsal fin set far back

***Stephanoberyx monae* (Pricklefish)**

Head is strongly convex and has prominent serrated ridges; pelvic fin is subabdominal

Trachichthyidae (Roughies)

Body oval, laterally compressed; head, eyes and mouth large; extensive sensory canals; flat, triangular spine on preopercle; reddish orange, pinkish or dusky silver in color

EX1711-D04
386 m

***Gephyroberyx darwinii* (Big Roughy)**

Lateral line scales slightly larger than body scales; prominent spine on opercle; dark spot at base of pectoral fins

Trachichthyidae (Roughies)

Body oval, laterally compressed; head, eyes and mouth large; extensive sensory canals; flat, triangular spine on preopercle; reddish orange, pinkish or dusky silver in color

***Hoplostethus occidentalis* (Western Roughy)**

Lateral line scales much larger than body scales; no prominent spine on opercle; pinkish in color

Berycidae (Alfonsinos)

Body oval, laterally compressed; head, eyes and mouth large; no spines on preopercle; bright red on head, back and fins, silvery pink on lower sides and belly

***Beryx decadactylus* (Red Bream)**

Head, body and fins bright red in color; body very deep (body depth 44-50% of SL); dorsal fin has 3-4 spines & 16-18 rays; eye diameter 14-17% of SL

Zeniontidae (Zeniontids)

Small oblong, laterally compressed body; mouth large; pelvic fins much longer than pectoral fins

Zenion hololepis (Dwarf Dory)

Body an elongate oval, strongly compressed; eye large; body dusky silver; dorsal fin with black patch at tip of front spines

Zeidae (Dories)

Oval fishes; head and body greatly compressed; mouth large, oblique, protrusible; body reddish or silvery

***Cyttopsis rosea* (Rosy Dory)**

Mouth large; spines absent on pelvic fins; thoracic region broad and flattened; rosy pink and silvery in color

Scorpaenidae (Scorpionfishes)

Mouth large; numerous head spines; dorsal fin with strong spines; large pectoral fins; strongly camouflaged, red or reddish brown in color with mottled color patterns

Helicolenus dactylopterus (Blackbelly Rosefish)

Dark red and white bars on body; small specimens have black spot on dorsal fin

Scorpaenidae (Scorpionfishes)

Mouth large; numerous head spines; dorsal fin with strong spines; large pectoral fins; strongly camouflaged, red or reddish brown in color with mottled color patterns

Idiastrion kyphos

Mostly red; strong head spines; juveniles have white blotch on upper back and caudal peduncle

Scorpaenidae (Scorpionfishes)

Mouth large; numerous head spines; dorsal fin with strong spines; large pectoral fins; strongly camouflaged, red or reddish brown in color with mottled color patterns

***Phenacoscorpius nebris* (Short-tube Scorpionfish)**

Head large with strong spines; eye large; head and body pinkish red with scattered small white blotches

Scorpaenidae (Scorpionfishes)

Mouth large; numerous head spines; dorsal fin with strong spines; large pectoral fins; strongly camouflaged, red or reddish brown in color with mottled color patterns

***Setarches guentheri* (Channeled Rockfish)**

Head large; 2nd preopercular spine well developed; pectoral rays 20-25; color is red, with dark red diagonal bars; spiny dorsal dark red to black

Scorpaenidae (Scorpionfishes)

Mouth large; numerous head spines; dorsal fin with strong spines; large pectoral fins; strongly camouflaged, red or reddish brown in color with mottled color patterns

***Trachyscorpia cristulata* (Atlantic Thornyhead)**

Pectoral fin square-cut with longest rays near upper edge of fin; head large; reddish with brown blotches and small white spots

Triglidae (Searobins)

Prolonged rostrum; lip and chin barbels present; 2 lower rays of pectoral fins free; external shell consisting of 4 rows of spinous scutes on each side

Peristedion greyae (Alligator Armored Searobin)

Rostral plates moderately long and narrow; head and body pink; fins with dark red edges; pectorals with dark red to blackish bars, white borders

Triglidae (Searobins)

Prolonged rostrum; lip and chin barbels present; 2 lower rays of pectoral fins free; external shell consisting of 4 rows of spinous scutes on each side

Peristedion truncatum (Black Armored Searobin)

Snout long, depressed; rostral plates moderately long; head and body reddish; outer edge of 1st dorsal dark red

Synagropidae (Splitfin Ocean-basses)

Oblong body; mouth large; caudal fin forked; dusky silver with black blotches

EX1711-D03
695 m

***Synagrops bellus* (Blackmouth Bass)**

Snout very short; eye large; head, body and fins sooty black; sides with dark chevron marks

Serranidae (Groupers)

Mouth moderate to large, terminal; rear edge of opercle with 3 flat spines; dorsal fin usually single

***Hyporthodus niveatus* (Snowy Grouper)**

Body robust, compressed, oval; color is dark brown with conspicuous white spots

Anthiadae (Fairy Basslets)

Caudal fin forked, lunate, emarginate, truncate, or rounded; mouth moderate to large, terminal; dorsal fin single; color is variable; many species capable of rapid color changes

***Anthias woodsi* (Swallowtail Bass)**

Caudal fin deeply forked, upper and lower lobes filamentous and long; mostly rose with broad yellow band; dorsal fin yellow in color

Epigonidae (Deepwater Cardinalfishes)

Eyes large; 1st dorsal with 6-8 spines, 2nd dorsal with 1 spine and 7-10 soft rays; lateral line extends onto caudal fin

Epigonus denticulatus (Pencil Cardinal)

Caudal peduncle elongated; body not deep; snout short and blunt; color is grayish brown and silvery green

Epigonidae (Deepwater Cardinalfishes)

Eyes large; 1st dorsal with 6-8 spines, 2nd dorsal with 1 spine and 7-10 soft rays; lateral line extends onto caudal fin

EX1711-D14
795 m

EX1711-D14
795 m

Epigonus macrops (Luminous Deepsea Cardinalfish)

Large scales; lacks an opercular spine; dorsal spines 8; huge eyes

Epigonidae (Deepwater Cardinalfishes)

Eyes large; 1st dorsal with 6-8 spines, 2nd dorsal with 1 spine and 7-10 soft rays; lateral line extends onto caudal fin

Epigonus occidentalis (Western Deepsea Cardinalfish)

Well-developed opercular spine present; dorsal spines 7, dorsal soft rays 10; color is blackish brown with fins grayish brown

Epigonidae (Deepwater Cardinalfishes)

Eyes large; 1st dorsal with 6-8 spines, 2nd dorsal with 1 spine and 7-10 soft rays; lateral line extends onto caudal fin

Epigonus oligolepis

Large scales; lacks an opercular spine; dorsal spines 7, dorsal soft rays 10

Epigonidae (Deepwater Cardinalfishes)

Eyes large; 1st dorsal with 6-8 spines, 2nd dorsal with 1 spine and 7-10 soft rays; lateral line extends onto caudal fin

Epigonus sp.

Zoarcidae (Eelpouts)

Eel-like body shape; snout short and blunt; single nostril on either side; pelvic fins absent or vestigial

Lycenchelys bullisi

Body short; large eyes; 2 lateral lines; scales absent from head; color is brown with dark fins

Chiasmodontidae (Swallowers)

Body moderately elongate; 2 dorsal fins; soft dorsal and anal fins elongate; lower jaw projecting beyond upper jaw; pelvic fins jugular

EX1711-D09
1133 m

EX1711-D09
1133 m

Chiasmodontidae

Bembropidae (Duckbills)

Head and anterior body flattened; eyes large, located dorsally; mouth large with lower jaw extending beyond upper

***Bembrops gobioides* (Goby Flathead)**

Membrane between 1st and 2nd spines of 1st dorsal fin dark gray; snout relatively short

Draconettidae (Deepwater Draconetts)

Dorsal fin with 3 strong spines; strong opercle and subopercle spines

***Centrodraco acanthopoma* (North-Atlantic Draconett)**

Head large; snout pointed; eyes very large; pinkish with 3 broad irregular whitish bars; top of eyeball white; fins mainly white

Trichiuridae (Cutlassfishes)

Caudal fin absent or forked; fang-like teeth; body long and ribbon-like; pelvic fins reduced or absent

Benthodesmus tenuis (Slender Frostfish)

Body silvery, jaws and opercle black; lower jaw projecting; caudal fin small, forked

Ariommatidae (Ariommas)

Small fishes; 2 dorsal fins, barely separated; caudal peduncle with low fleshy keels; eye moderate to large; color is silvery with a purple, brown or blue tinge

***Ariomma bondi* (Silver-rag)**

Body slender, rounded; eye large; 2 low fleshy keels on base of caudal fin; caudal fin strongly forked; color is dark blue on back, silver below; juveniles with 3-6 dark bars on sides

Centrolophidae (Medusafishes)

Snout blunt and thick; single continuous dorsal fin; pelvic fins below or just behind pectoral fins

***Hyperoglyphe perciformis* (Barrelfish)**

Snout length greater than eye; pelvic fin origin under base of pectoral; adults dark, greenish to brownish

Xiphiidae (Swordfishes)

Premaxilla & nasal bones extremely elongated, forming a pointed, depressed, sharp-edged sword

EX1711-D15
533 m

***Xiphias gladius* (Swordfish)**

Blackish-brown fading to light-brown below; 1st dorsal fin with blackish-brown membrane, other fins brown or blackish-brown; a long, flat, sword-like bill and no pelvic fins

Bothidae (Lefteye Flounders)

Eyes on left side; margin of preopercle free; dorsal and anal fins separate from caudal

***Monolene sessilicauda* (Deepwater Flounder)**

Head pointed; lateral line strongly arched; pectoral with dotted cross-bars; tail fin with central oval dark blotch

Poecilopsettidae (Bigeye Flounders)

Eyes on right side; margin of preopercle free

Poecilopsetta beanii (Deepwater Dab)

Eyes large; color is brown with small dark blotches; caudal fin with large dark blotches

Cynoglossidae (Tongue Soles)

Eyes on left side; eyes and mouth small; pectoral fins absent; dorsal and anal fins joined to caudal fin

***Symphurus marginatus* (Margined Tonguefish)**

Top side uniformly brown with a dark blotch covering tail and tail base; no lateral line

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